

INTEGRATED DISEASE MANAGEMENT OF RAPESEED AND MUSTARD.

Sourik Poddar*

Uttar Banga Krishi Vishwavidyalaya, Pundibari-736165, West Bengal, India

*Corresponding author: sourikpoddar1997@gmail.com

Received: May 02, 2021; Accepted: July 02, 2021

Introduction

Mustard (*Brassica juncea*), India's most important edible oilseed brassica crop, has long been cultivated as a pure crop as well as an intercrop (or mixed crop) in marginal and submarginal soils in the country's eastern, northern, and north western states. The luxuriant growth and productivity of mustard in these states is largely due to the cool, moist climate of the winter months. In the Central and Southern states, where the winter climate is milder, mustard is cultivated only as a mixed crop for seed that is used for condiments.

The state of Haryana has the highest mustard productivity (1559 kg ha⁻¹) and Assam has the lowest (524 kg ha⁻¹) with a national average of 900-1150 kg ha⁻¹, which is the actually harvested yield and is always a fraction of the attainable yield of 2500-3000 kg ha⁻¹ due to unmanaged or inadequately managed major diseases and pests at various phenological stages of the plant. *Alternaria* blight (*Alternaria brassicae*), white rust + downy mildew complex (*Albugo candida* + *Hyaloperonospora parasitica*), Sclerotinia stem rot (*Sclerotinia sclerotiorum*), and powdery mildew (*Erysiphe cruciferarum*) are among the most economically significant pathogens.

Major diseases and their Management

1. White rust

Causal organism- *Albugo candida* or *A. cruciferarum*

Economic importance: The disease first appears in early January, shortly after Alternaria leaf blight attacks the undersides of lower leaves.

Symptoms: There is evidence of both local and systemic contamination. Isolated white/creamy yellow elevated pustules develop on the underside of leaves in cases of local infection, which then coalesce to form patches. Hypertrophy and hyperplasia are caused by systemic inflammation, resulting in malformation and distortion of floral sections. A bloated sterile structure replaces the entire inflorescence (Stag head). When a widespread inflammation of the stem is discovered, the injury is at its peak.

Pathogen: The fungus is an obligate parasite. The fungus's mycelium is non-septate and intercellular, resulting in knob-like haustoria. The mycelium on which sporangia are formed in a basipetal succession produces a large number of short sporangiophores. Oogonia and antheridia enter through a fertilisation tube in a systemic infection, resulting in oospore. In a vesicle, oospores germinate to become zoospores. The zoospores are biflagellate and elliptical to kidney shaped.

Disease cycle: The fungus reproduces by forming oospores in the tissues of infected hosts. The zoospores disseminated by rain or irrigation water are the secondary mode of transmission.

Management

- Collection and destruction of contaminated plant debris
- Collection and destruction of contaminated plant debris
- Rotation of non-cruciferous crops • Seed sowing early (in first week of October)
- Metalaxyl (Apron 35SD)@6g/kg seed, followed by a single spray of Metalaxyl (Ridomyl MZ)@0.2 percent
- Plant resistant varieties such as RC 781, PYSR 8, and PR 10, as well as tolerant varieties such as Kranthi and Krishna.

2. Downy mildew

Causal organism-*Peronospora parasitica*

Symptoms: Symptoms may occur on any aerial section, but leaves and inflorescence are the most common. On the lower surface of the leaves, greyish white irregular necrotic patches appear. The inflammation of inflorescence, which causes hypertrophy of the peduncle or inflorescence, is the most visible and pronounced symptom (Stag head). There are no siliqua or seeds produced by the affected inflorescence.

Pathogen: The fungus is an obligate parasite. The fungus's mycelium is non-septate, intercellular, and develops haustoria. Sporangioophores have sterigmata that are dichotomously branched with acute angles that are typically of similar length. The pointed sterigmata contain oval and non-papillate sporangia. Sporangia are often germinated into a germ tube and act like conidia.

Disease cycle: The fungus reproduces by forming oospores in the tissues of infected hosts and on weed hosts. Wind-borne sporangia is the secondary mode of transmission.

Management

- Gather and dispose of contaminated plant debris with $\frac{3}{4}$ non-cruciferous crop rotation
- Seed dressing with Metalaxyl (Apron 35SD)@6g/kg seed followed by a single spray with Metalaxyl (Ridomyl MZ)@0.2 percent in the first week of October
- Plant tolerant varieties such as RC 781, PYSR 8, and PR 10 in your garden.

3. Powdery mildew

Causal organism: *Erysiphe cruciferarum*

Symptoms: Dirty white circular spots occur on both sides of lower leaves as symptoms. When the climate is favourable, the leaves, roots, and siliquae are all influenced. The siliquae that have been infected yield thin, shrivelled seeds.

Pathogen: The disease is ectophytic, extending through the leaf's surface and injecting haustoria into epidermal cells. Conidiophores, which develop vertically from the leaf surface and carry conidia in small chains, are called conidiophores. Conidia belong to the *Oidium* genus. Cleistothecia emerge later in the season as tiny black globose structures with myceloid appendages. Each ascus contains 3-8 elliptical, hyaline, single-celled ascospores, and each cleistothecium contains 4-8 asci.

Disease cycle: The fungus overwinters as ascospores or mycelium on volunteer host plants via cleistothecia. Conidia carried by the wind spread the disease.

Favourable conditions: Dry weather favours the disease, which becomes more serious in irrigated areas.

Management

- Spray the seed with wettable sulphur at 0.2 percent, Dinocap at 0.1 percent, or tridemorph at 0.1 percent to collect and remove contaminated plant debris.

4. *Alternaria* leaf spot

Causal organism: *Alternaria brassicae* and *A. brassicola*

Economic importance - *A. brassicae* causes a more serious disease that affects all rapeseed-mustard growing areas.

Symptoms: Spots appear on the branches, stems, and siliquae as the disease progresses. *A. brassicae* spots are normally grey in colour, as opposed to *A. brassicola*'s dark sooty velvety spots.

Pathogen: Conidiophores with a single conidium at the apex are dark brown, slender, septate, irregularly bent conidiophores produced by the fungus. Obclavate, medium to dark brown in

color, with both transverse and longitudinal septa and a conspicuous beak, the conidia are obclavate.

Disease cycle: The pathogen persists as latent mycelium in contaminated seed debris. Airborne conidia are the primary mode of secondary transmission.

Management

- Residue from contaminated plants must be removed and destroyed.
- Use disease-free or disease-treated seed (Mancozeb @2.5g/kg seed) and spray with mancozeb (0.25%) or Iprodione (0.2%) per 10 days.

Conclusion and future prospect (Naresh *et al.*, 2020).

- Alternaria blight, white rust, downy mildew, powdery mildew, and white stem rot are the five main diseases that affect rapeseed-mustard and cause significant quantitative and qualitative losses.
- Cultural practises such as field sanitation, clean cultivation, timely sowing, adjusting sowing dates based on disease occurrence in the region, destruction of disease debris after harvesting, deep summer ploughing during May-June, use of proper fertiliser doses, timely and proper irrigation, and crop rotation at least three years of non-cruciferous crops ploughed.
- Deploying resistant varieties everywhere helps to reduce disease-related losses.
- Disease prediction models, wherever they are created, can be extremely useful in deploying disease management practises in a timely manner.
- Fungicides, bioagents, botanicals, organic amendments, and other treatments developed for specific diseases should be used at prescribed doses to limit disease losses.
- Designing epidemic forecasting models by analysing the interactions between the host, pathogen, and climate.
- The development of basic and practical disease prediction models.
- Data management, collection, retrieval, analysis, and display using information technology (IT).
- Genes for gradual white rusting, disease tolerance, and partial resistance have been discovered.

References

Course Material For Path 371 Diseases Of Field Crops And Their Management Prepared By Dr. P. Kishore Varma, Assistant Professor, Department Of Plant Pathology Agricultural College, Aswaraopet 507 301

Naresh Mehta Development of prediction models for the management of rapeseed-mustard diseases Current scenario 2020 *Plant Disease Research* **34** (2) : 81-112